

FREE VIBRATION CHARACTERISTICS INVESTIGATION IN COMPOSITE LAMINATED OPEN CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

SHAH NAZIM SULTAN*, PROF. AHER HARSHAL

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14452000>MAZEDAN TRANSACTIONS ON
ENGINEERING SYSTEMS DESIGN

e-ISSN: 2582-8061

Article id-MTESD0502006

Vol-5, Issue-2

Received: 16 Aug 2024

Revised: 27 Oct 2024

Accepted: 30 Nov 2024

Citation: Shah N. S., & Harshal, A. (2024). Free Vibration Characteristics Investigation in Composite Laminated Open Cylindrical Shells. *Mazedan Transactions on Engineering Systems Design*, 5(2), 22–24.

Abstract

The shell vibration problem is of continuing interest due to their rampant use as structural members. Often these shells are made of laminated composites. These laminated shells have a very wide range of applications, particularly in aerospace, military hardware, marine ships, and civil constructions, as well as an integral part of machines where they are subjected to dynamic loading hence their vibratory analysis, is important for efficient, reliable and failure-proof design. Composite laminated open shells in these applications are employed with various boundary conditions. Understanding the vibration characteristics of these shell components is particularly important for engineers to design suitable structures with low vibration and noise radiation characteristics. The present work investigates the free vibration characteristics of composite laminated open cylindrical shells for general boundary conditions using a unified Chebyshev-Ritz formulation. The Rayleigh-Ritz method based on the energy functional of the open cylindrical shell has been used to obtain solutions. The method has been validated with standard reference and a convergence test of this method has also been done. A parametric study has been done including the effect of aspect ratio, lamination scheme, width-to-radius ratio, thickness-to-radius ratio, and boundary conditions. The analytical results have also been compared with the numerical results obtained using finite element solver ANSYS.

Keywords: Free Vibration, Composites, Laminated Cylinder Shell, Simulation, Rayleigh-Ritz.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development in material science and material processing technology the composite materials have a growing application in the industry [1]. Being an important structural component, the cylindrical shells and panels made up of laminated composite are extensively used in numerous engineering applications, for example aeroplane, spacecraft, ships, and many civil engineering structures. While designing any structure its determination of vibration characteristics is an important part of the analysis [2]. Therefore, such analyses for shell structure have always been a subject of research which offers a good understanding of the dynamic behaviour that is very helpful while designing such structures optimally made up of composite materials [3]. With growing application of composite shell structures has attracted researchers for the development of shell theories and mathematical models that are accurate and efficient at the same time. Over the time there has been a noteworthy advancement in the field of dynamic analysis of composite shells [4, 5].

Researchers have given many theories for the analysis of the shells from classical to a large number of modern theories including several solution methodologies [6, 7]. Different application areas of laminated composite shells are shown in Figure 1.

The free vibration analysis of generally supported composite laminated open cylindrical shells has been

carried out by using the unified Chebyshev-Ritz formulation, The convergence and accuracy of the present formulation are checked by a considerable number of convergence tests and comparisons.

Figure 1 application areas of laminated composite shells

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

After formulating the shell vibration problem using the kinematics the formulated problem needs to be solved and there has been a lot of effort put by the researchers in developing solution methodologies to solve these formulations accurately and efficiently. There have been

many solution methods existing for the analysis of vibration of shells. Rayleigh-Ritz and finite element method are being extensively employed for the solution among many and in our present study also going to use Rayleigh-Ritz method to solve our problem analytically and then these results will be compared with FEA software (ANSYS) results. The details of the flow of the methodology are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Steps involved in the analysis of laminated composite structures

2.1 Boundary conditions

Most of the work done in the past in the vibration analysis of shell is related to classical boundary conditions only. But in real world applications the shell structures are subjected to various boundary conditions other than classical ones. Very limited work has been done regarding the shell vibration with general boundary conditions and that too recently.

Figure 3 Defining boundary conditions using springs

2.2 Case Study

Figure 4 shows the cylindrical coordinate system and geometric dimensions for the analysis of laminated composite cylindrical panel. x is the longitudinal direction, Θ is the angular direction and z represents the thickness direction. Dimension of the shell varies from zero L and in angular direction it varies from zero to Θ_0 , the reference surface is taken in the middle plane. Total number of layers of shell is denoted by N_L and thickness of each layer is taken same and assumed that it remains constant. The distance of k^{th} layer bottom and upper surface from the reference plane in the z direction is denoted by z^k and z^{k+1} respectively.

Figure 4 Coordinate system for cylindrical shells

According to the FSDT assumptions, i.e., the transverse normal do not remain perpendicular to the mid surface after the deformation. This amounts to including transverse shear strain in the theory. The inextensibility of transverse normal requires that w not be a function of thickness coordinate z . The displacements u, v, w in the x, Θ and z direction respectively can be expressed as equations (1-3):

$$u(x, \theta, z, t) = u_0(x, \theta, t) + z\phi_x(x, \theta, t) \tag{1}$$

$$v(x, \theta, z, t) = v_0(x, \theta, t) + z\phi_\theta(x, \theta, t) \tag{2}$$

$$w(x, \theta, z, t) = w_0(x, \theta, t) \tag{3}$$

In this expression t denotes the time. Displacement of any point on the reference plane is denoted by u_0, v_0, w_0 in the x, Θ and z direction respectively. For representing the rotations of transverse normal the notation ϕ_x and ϕ_θ in the Θ and x -direction respectively is used.

3. RESULTS

Using Chebyshev-Ritz solution, the following results for non-dimensional frequency parameters $\Omega = \omega L^2 \sqrt{\rho h/D}$ are obtained for 4-layer angle ply laminated composite cylindrical panel with all the edges free and compared with the results obtained by Tiangui [8]. By observing the results closely, as shown in Table 1 we can see the efficiency of the present solution technique as the results are very close to that of other higher-order theory.

Comparison between the results obtained by the analytical study and that from the ANSYS has been made for the first five natural frequencies and their corresponding mode shapes has been plotted. From Figure 5 it can be seen that as the width to radius ratio increases the non-dimensional frequencies decrease. The non-dimensional frequency parameter is maximum for $b/R=1$ and minimum for $b/R=0.3333$ for all the modes of vibration. The trend observed here is correct and the results obtained are in good agreement with the ANSYS results. In other words, it can be said that as the shell becomes shallower the non-dimensional frequency parameter decreases for all the mode of

Table 1 Comparison of non-dimensional natural frequencies for four-layer (-60/60/60/-60) subjected to FFFF

MODAL FREQ	MXN	11X11	12X12	13X13	14X14	15X15
I	Present	3.256	3.255	3.256	3.257	3.256
	Reference [8]	3.244	3.2422	3.2422	3.2404	3.2404
II	Present	5.5680	5.571	5.572	5.574	5.572
	Reference [8]	5.5872	5.5869	5.5868	5.5866	5.5866
III	Present	8.4814	8.482	8.473	8.481	8.479
	Reference [8]	8.3682	8.3672	8.3639	8.3629	8.3598
IV	Present	11.123	11.129	11.124	11.124	11.125
	Reference [8]	11.114	11.112	11.109	11.107	11.105
V	Present	12.953	12.964	12.956	12.953	12.956
	Reference [8]	12.495	12.494	12.488	12.487	12.488

Figure 5 Effect of width to radius ratio on natural frequencies for four-layer (0-90-0-90) subjected to SSSS boundary conditions

4. CONCLUSIONS

The free vibration analysis of generally supported composite laminated open cylindrical shells has been carried out by using the unified Chebyshev–Ritz formulation. The convergence and accuracy of the present formulation are checked by a considerable number of convergence tests and comparisons. The formulation in the present study gives accurate results for general boundary conditions. For all the edges clamped the frequency of vibration is highest and lowest for the cantilevered panel clamped along the longitudinal direction. As the number of layers in the lamination scheme increases the natural frequency of vibration increases and this effect becomes insignificant for large number of layers. With increase of aspect ratio, the natural frequency vibration decreases for all modes. With increasing thickness of the shell, the non-dimensional frequency parameter for the shell decreases. With increase in width to radius ratio the non-dimensional frequency parameter increases.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bhong, M., Khan, T. K., Devade, K., Krishna, B. V., Sura, S., Eftikhaar, H. K., ... & Gupta, N. (2023). Review of composite materials and applications. *Materials Today: Proceedings*.
- [2] Aloisio, A., Pasca, D. P., De Santis, Y., Hillberger, T., Giordano, P. F., Rosso, M. M., ... & Bedon, C. (2023). Vibration issues in timber structures: A state-of-the-art review. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 76, 107098.
- [3] Naem, S., Patil, A. V., Shaikh, A. V., Shinde, U. P., Husain, D., Alam, M. T., ... & Ahmad, A. (2023). A Review of Cobalt-Based Metal Hydroxide Electrode for Applications in Supercapacitors. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, 2023(1), 1133559.
- [4] Leissa, A.W. (1973) *Vibration of Shells*. NASA SP288 (US Government Printing Office, Washington, DC) Republished in 1993 by The Acoustical Society of America
- [5] Dong, S. B. (1968). Free vibration of laminated orthotropic cylindrical shells. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 44(6), 1628-1635.
- [6] Li S. (2004) Vibration analysis of rectangular plates with general elastic boundary supports. *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 273,3, 619-635.
- [7] Zhang X. (2009) Vibrations of rectangular plates with arbitrary non-uniform elastic edge restraints. *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 326,1-2, 221-234.

- [8] Tiangui Y. (2014) A unified Chebyshev-Ritz formulation for vibration analysis of composite laminated deep open shells with arbitrary boundary conditions. *Archive of Applied Mechanics* 84, 4 441-471.